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Attribute preferences for plant-based meat analogs – Consumer segments in four European food cultures

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ABSTRACT

Plant-based meat analogs could support a transition toward a more sustainable food system, but consumer acceptance is currently low. Using a rating-based conjoint design, this study investigated what preferences consumers have in relation to different product attributes and how these preferences are distributed across distinct European food cultures. The impacts of the following product attributes were tested: type of meat product being imitated, main protein-rich ingredient, price, and front-of-package claims presenting information about the nutritional content (protein, fiber, and vitamin B12) and quality (naturalness, country of origin, and meat-like taste) of the product. Data from 2986 participants in Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia were collected via an online questionnaire. A cluster analysis was conducted to identify consumer clusters with distinct preferences and established scales for food-related psychological traits were used to further characterize these clusters. The largest consumer cluster could best be described as indifferent toward the tested product attributes. However, a substantial share of consumers reacted positively to lower prices and to meat analogs that imitate a processed meat product (burger patty) instead of a whole cut (steak). In addition, country-specific preferences for the main protein-rich ingredient were identified. The front-of-package claims had no meaningful impact on any consumer cluster. Based on these results, product developers should focus on offering affordable options for promising product types and take country-specific preferences into account. However, the findings also indicate that additional efforts beyond product design are required to reach the majority of indifferent consumers.

1. Introduction

The substantial environmental impact associated with the production of animal-based food calls for a dietary transition toward more alternative protein sources (Aiking & De Boer, 2020). In particular, beef and lamb production leads to especially high greenhouse gas emissions and agricultural land use (Poore & Nemecek, 2019). In Europe, meat consumption has decreased only slightly in recent years (Eurostat, 2024), and meat is still the most important source of protein (Daas et al., 2025). Having been a crucial part of human evolution and history, shaping cultures and traditions around the globe (Leroy & Praet, 2015), the consumption of meat is still considered the norm in many places, hindering a shift toward more plant-based diets (Piazza et al., 2015).

Replacing meat products with plant-based alternatives could substantially lower the environmental impact of consumers' diets and is also associated with certain nutrition and health benefits (Springmann, 2024). Products that mimic the sensory properties of meat are commonly referred to as meat analogs (Fischer et al., 2022), and many hoped that the introduction of new plant-based meat analogs would facilitate a transition toward more plant-based diets (Lonkila & Kaljonen, 2021). However, acceptance of meat analogs remains limited (Onwezen et al., 2021) and there are no signs of substantial substitution effects (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023).

The literature suggests that environmental benefits alone cannot convince consumers to substitute meat with meat analogs but that sensory appeal, health, and price are more important drivers (Onwezen

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& Dagevos, 2024). Assessing the healthiness of plant-based meat analogs currently on the market is complex. Although there are some nutritional benefits, such as higher fiber and lower saturated fat content, protein quality is generally lower, and the bioavailability of protein and other nutrients is limited (Domic et al., 2025; El Sadig & Wu, 2024; Xie et al., 2024). While plant-based products could help alleviate the current fiber deficiency in many European countries (Daas et al., 2025), they do not naturally contain vitamin B12. Fortifying meat analogs with vitamin B12 could be important for avoiding deficiencies in people who aim to completely substitute meat (Mariotti, 2025). Overall, there is a lack of studies investigating the long-term health effects of replacing meat with meat analogs (Lindberg et al., 2024). When it comes to sensory appeal, some meat analogs achieve good results in sensory studies (Bakhsh et al., 2021; Sogari et al., 2023), but there remain many challenges, such as sensory off-notes and a lack of juiciness (Giacalone et al., 2022). Most studies have indicated that sensory expectations for meat analogs have not yet been met (Dutra da Silva et al., 2025). Another barrier for meat analogs is their often high degree of processing and low perceived naturalness (Varela et al., 2022). Consumers often assume that natural products and processes are inherently better, known as the “natural is better bias” (Meier et al., 2019), which is a particularly powerful heuristic when judging new food technologies (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020).

Although plant-based meat analogs face multiple challenges, they are currently more promising than insect-based or cell-based products (Etter et al., 2024; Pronk et al., 2025). More plant-based meat analogs are expected to enter the market (Good Food Institute, 2025), and aside from production advancements that could improve product qualities (such as taste), the question remains how many consumers can be convinced by focusing on certain product types or by optimizing the attribute configurations of products. While some attributes, such as the main protein-rich ingredient, have been investigated more intensively in recent years (Onwezen et al., 2021), others have received much less examination. In addition, product attributes are often investigated in isolation, which makes it hard to quantify their impact when consumers consider multiple attributes simultaneously, such as in real shopping situations. Through a rating-based conjoint analysis, the present study investigates the extent to which the type of meat product being imitated (burger patty versus steak), the main protein-rich ingredient (peas versus soy), and the price (115%, 100%, 85%, and 70% of the average meat price) impact consumers' preferences for meat analogs. Additionally, the study assesses the effectiveness of different claims about the nutritional content (protein, fiber, and vitamin B12) and the quality of the product (naturalness, country of origin, and meat-like taste). The current knowledge about each of these attributes is discussed in detail in Section 1.1.

Relying solely on average effects can paint a distorted picture of the impact of product attributes (Godden et al., 2023). To avoid this, the present study complements the results of the conjoint analysis with a cluster analysis, providing a more nuanced picture of how many consumers actually have attribute preferences and how many are indifferent. Consumer clusters are further described using food-related psychological traits (see Section 1.2 for more details) and by analyzing their distribution in four European countries (Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia) with distinct consumption patterns and food traditions (see Section 1.3 for more details).

1.1. Attributes of meat analogs

1.1.1. Type of meat product being imitated

Some meat analogs imitate products that are processed, such as burger patties, sausages, and nuggets, while others imitate less processed whole cuts, such as steaks and chicken breasts. Consumers have been shown to perceive more similarities between processed meat products and their plant-based counterparts than between unprocessed meat products and their plant-based counterparts (Hoek et al., 2011; Michel et al., 2021). It has been argued that it is easier for consumers to

imagine a plant-based analog for meat products that have themselves been physically changed and reshaped (e.g., burger patties or nuggets) than for whole cuts, such as steaks, in which the animal flesh is featured more prominently (Hoek et al., 2011). The use of spices and breading can further facilitate the convincing imitation of processed meat products (Michel et al., 2021). However, most studies focused on only one type of meat analog (most often plant-based burger patties). To test the impact of the type of meat product being imitated on consumers' preferences for meat analogs, in the present study, a plant-based burger patty is compared with a plant-based steak.

1.1.2. Main protein-rich ingredients

Research has consistently shown that plant-based meat alternatives are more accepted by consumers than insect-based meat alternatives and cultured meat (Onwezen et al., 2021). However, within the category of plant-based ingredients, differences in consumer acceptance have been found as well (Etter et al., 2024; Pronk et al., 2025). So far, it is unclear whether these effects can also be found when consumers are presented with complete product profiles and have to make trade-offs between different attributes. To test how much attention consumers actually pay to the main protein-rich ingredient, products made from pea and soy are compared. Pea and soy are among the most widely used protein sources for meat alternatives (Lindberg et al., 2024), but pea has been shown to be more accepted than soy across multiple European countries (Pronk et al., 2025).

1.1.3. Price

Besides taste, price is the most important driver of consumers' food purchases (Markovina et al., 2015). In most countries, meat analogs are currently more expensive than meat (Siegrist, Green, Michel and Mathys, 2024), which has been identified as a major barrier for consumers (Jahn et al., 2024; Siegrist, Michel and Hartmann, 2024). In the current study, prices are tested ranging from noticeably more expensive than meat products to substantially cheaper than meat products (115%, 100%, 85%, and 70% of the average meat price) to cover current and potential future price levels.

1.1.4. Nutrition claims

Although there is a lack of data on the use of nutrition claims in Europe, studies analyzing products on the Australian and US markets have found that almost every plant-based meat analog features a nutritional claim (Brooker et al., 2022; Lacy-Nichols et al., 2021). These studies identified protein, fiber, vitamin B12, and iron as the most frequently advertised nutrients in meat analogs. In the European Union, such claims can be used as long as the products adhere to minimum requirements regarding the content of nutrients per product weight or energy value (Regulation, 1924/2006). Although not an EU member, Serbia follows the same regulation (Davidovic et al., 2021). Despite the widespread use of nutrition claims, very few studies have investigated whether they actually increase consumers' preference for meat analogs. A recent study by Naughton et al. (2025) found such claims to be much less influential than the products' meat- versus plant-based nature or price. In contrast to Naughton et al. (2025), the present study investigates the importance of nutrition claims in comparison to other product attributes within the category of meat analogs. To do this, claims about the three most often advertised nutrients in meat analogs were selected: protein, fiber, and vitamin B12.

1.1.5. Quality claims

In a series of influential studies, Rozin and colleagues showed that humans have a strong preference for natural entities, especially when it comes to food (Rozin et al., 2004). Even small amounts of additives drastically decrease people's naturalness perceptions of foods (Rozin, 2005), and food processing negatively affects naturalness perceptions independently of the product's final state (Rozin, 2006). The tendency to equate naturalness with better quality in the food domain is often

referred to as the natural is better bias (Meier et al., 2019). Increasing the perception of naturalness is therefore an important part of improving consumers' acceptance of meat analogs (Jahn et al., 2021; Varela et al., 2022). Food marketers often take advantage of consumers' preference for naturalness by applying naturalness claims to products (Business Research Insights, 2025). There are currently no explicit guidelines in European legislation regarding the use of such claims, which raises concerns about potential misuse (Radaelli et al., 2025). Despite these concerns, very few studies have tested the effect of naturalness claims on consumers' perceptions of food products. These studies suggest that naturalness claims can increase purchase intentions (Schirmacher et al., 2023) and improve product perception (Radaelli et al., 2025). As long as naturalness claims do not disappoint consumers' expectations, they could be an effective marketing tool for tackling negative processing perceptions toward meat analogs.

Across food products and cultures, research shows that consumers prefer food products from their own country (Thøgersen, 2023). When it comes to meat, studies have shown that the country of origin is the most important quality cue for consumers (Aboah & Lees, 2020). However, only a few studies have tested how country-of-origin claims affect perceptions of meat analogs, finding mixed results regarding their impact (Giezenaar et al., 2024; Meixner et al., 2024; Weinrich & Elshiewy, 2019).

Although heuristic cues, such as perceived naturalness and country of origin, can influence the overall quality perception of a product, consumers' taste expectations remain the most important barrier for the purchases of meat analogs (Giacalone et al., 2022). In the present study, it is therefore tested how a claim that directly addresses consumers' taste motives performs. Some studies have already investigated the extent to which the use of hedonic descriptions can improve the perception of plant-based dishes and found promising results (Farrar et al., 2024; Greene et al., 2024). The present study tests whether taste claims also work on product packaging. Based on previous research suggesting that a large share of consumers would prefer meat analogs to taste like meat (Michel et al., 2021), the effectiveness of a "tastes like meat" claim is tested.

1.2. Influence of consumer characteristics

It is likely that consumer preferences are not uniform but that consumer segments with distinct preferences exist. Other studies showed that simply averaging effects across respondents can conceal the true effects of product attributes and lead to biased recommendations (Godden et al., 2023). To avoid this, the present study conducted a cluster analysis based on the unveiled preferences of the participants. By describing the food motives and attitudes of these consumer segments, it is possible to get further insights into the reasons for their preferences. Consumers with high food neophobia (reluctance to try new foods, see: Pliner & Hobden, 1992) may be more sensitive to the ingredients used and to the type of meat product being imitated because these attributes determine their familiarity with the products. Consumers who find it important that the food they eat is natural and sustainable are likely to react more positively to a naturalness claim or a country-of-origin claim. In contrast, consumers who are particularly health conscious are expected to prefer meat analogs with nutrition claims, and those who are highly committed to eating meat might react more positively to a claim about the meat-like taste of a product. In addition, some consumers may hold strong negative attitudes toward meat alternatives and therefore show different attribute preferences than other consumers. Established scales measuring meat commitment (Piazza et al., 2015), meat alternative rejection (Wassmann et al., 2025), food neophobia (Pliner & Hobden, 1992), naturalness motive (Stephoe et al., 1995), ecological welfare motive (Lindeman & Väänänen, 2000), and health consciousness (Dohle et al., 2014; Schifferstein & Oude Ophuis, 1997) have been used in the present study to describe these tendencies.

1.3. Food cultures

People in different European countries are familiar with different types of ingredients and foods, and their cultural backgrounds strongly influence their food preferences (Rozin, 1996). To take cultural differences into account, data for this study were collected in four European countries with distinct dietary traditions: Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia. Although the selected countries cannot be considered representative of other countries, with every European country being unique, each of these countries shares some of their cuisine and food culture with a wider culinary region.

Finland is part of the Scandinavian food landscape, which has been strongly shaped by the Nordic climate and the need to preserve food for the long winter season (Amilien & Notaker, 2018). There are still many similarities between the Scandinavian countries, such as a high intake of dairy products, fish, rye bread, and grains such as oats (Amilien & Notaker, 2018). Today, pork is the most consumed meat in Finland, followed by poultry and beef, but for the northern parts of Finland, reindeer husbandry remains an important feature (Mäkelä & Rautavirta, 2018).

German food culture shows many similarities with other central European and, especially, other German-speaking countries (Switzerland and Austria). Pork is the most commonly eaten meat, and ham and sausages are particularly popular (Strassner, 2020).

The traditional Italian diet is often described as an example of the Mediterranean diet, characterized by a high intake of olive oil, cereals, fresh or dried fruit and vegetables, and only a moderate amount of fish, dairy, and meat (UNESCO, 2010). Although there are some consistent patterns, the Mediterranean countries are not homogenous, and studies have observed a shift from the traditional Mediterranean diet in Italy toward a more Westernized and less healthy diet (CIHEAM/FAO, 2015).

Serbia and other Balkan countries share, in large parts, the same food culture due to the long-lasting domination of this region by the Ottoman Empire (Jianu & Barbu, 2018). Characteristics of Balkan cuisine include grilled, dried, and smoked meats and dairy products, especially yogurt. Home cooking and baking remain very common, and the culture has been described as respecting and valuing food (Krsteva-Blagoeva & Bogueva, 2021).

In a recent study investigating protein consumption patterns in Europe (Daas et al., 2025), Germany was found to have more consumers with a common protein consumption close to the average European consumption pattern. In contrast, Finland had more consumers with health-conscious protein consumption (e.g., higher amounts of yogurt, eggs, and wholegrain products), Italy had more consumers with traditional protein consumption (e.g., higher amounts of ruminant meat, offal meat, seafood, and cheese), and Serbia had more consumers with fast-food protein consumption (e.g., higher amounts of processed meat, nonruminant meat, and refined bread). In addition, a recent study found that consumers from Finland and Serbia had higher meat commitment values than those from the other two countries, with meat alternative rejection particularly high in Serbia (Pronk et al., 2025).

1.4. Aims of the present study

This study investigated what preferences consumers have in relation to different product attributes of plant-based meat analogs and how these preferences are distributed across distinct European food cultures. Specifically, the preferences for the following attributes are tested: type of meat product being imitated (burger patty versus steak), main protein-rich ingredient (peas versus soy), and price (115%, 100%, 85%, and 70% of the meat price) as well as the impact of front-of-package claims regarding nutrition (protein, fiber, and vitamin B12) and product quality (naturalness, country of origin, and meat-like taste). To take the diversity of European consumers into account, the study was conducted in four countries with particular food cultures and culinary traditions (Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia). The combination of

conjoint analysis and cluster analysis enables a nuanced assessment of preferences that goes beyond average effects. This will help product developers to focus on the aspects that are most likely to increase the appeal of plant-based meat analogs to consumers. Knowing how consumer segments with different preferences are distributed across different countries will help marketers to promote their products more effectively.

2. Methods

2.1. Study participants

An online survey, programmed on the platform Qualtrics (Provo, UT, USA), was distributed in Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia in April 2025. A professional panel provider (Bilendi GmbH, Berlin, Germany) was used to recruit the participants, who were compensated according to the panel provider's reimbursement plan. A quota sampling method was applied to achieve an even distribution of men and women as well as of age groups (20–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59, or 60+) in each country. Participants had to be at least 20 years old and fluent in their country's main language (Finnish, German, Italian, or Serbian). Participants who failed to correctly answer two simple attention checks or who finished the survey unusually quickly (less than half of the median duration of the respective country) were excluded from the data analysis. In addition, participants who showed zero variance in their ratings of the products shown in the conjoint task were excluded. This was necessary because estimating part-worth utilities for participants who showed no variance in their ratings would be uninformative. More importantly, it can be assumed that the participants who did not differentiate the products at all did not pay attention to the task (Krosnick, 1991). After data cleaning, a final sample of 2986 participants remained for data analysis. The final sample consisted of 27% of participants from Finland, 25% from Germany, 23% from Italy, and 26% from Serbia. Slightly more participants identified as women (54%), and the mean age of the sample was 45 years (SD = 15). A detailed description of the country samples can be found in Table 2 (Section 3.1). The participants remained anonymous throughout the study, and the study design was approved by the ethics commission of ETH Zurich (proposal no. 25 ETHICS-050).

2.2. Questionnaire

The questionnaire was first developed in English and then translated into the languages of the four target countries (Finnish, German, Italian, and Serbian). A translation and back-translation were conducted with two independent native speakers from each country to prevent unintended changes in the meaning of the items. The survey questionnaire started by providing general information about the study, as well as a consent form. The rest of the survey was structured into four main parts: sociodemographics, a rating-based conjoint task, variables from the theory of planned behavior that explain meat reduction intentions, and food-related consumer traits. The variables from the theory of planned behavior were not relevant for the present article and will be reported elsewhere. They were placed after the conjoint task to rule out any effects of the scales used on the participants' product ratings in the conjoint task. The median time taken for participants to complete the questionnaire was 12.9 min.

2.2.1. Sociodemographics

In the first part of the questionnaire, participants' gender, age, highest education level, and self-identified dietary style were assessed. Options for dietary styles were accompanied by a short description: omnivore ("I regularly eat meat"), flexitarian ("I only eat meat rarely"), pescetarian ("I do not eat meat, but I eat fish and seafood"), vegetarian ("I eat neither meat nor fish and seafood"), and vegan ("I do not eat animal-based products at all").

2.2.2. Rating-based conjoint task

The second and main part of the questionnaire consisted of a rating-based conjoint task. In this task, participants rated how likely they were to buy 18 different plant-based meat analogs. A detailed description and reasoning behind the experimental design can be found in Section 2.3.

2.2.3. Consumer characteristics

In the final part of the survey, validated scales to measure the importance of naturalness for food choices, the importance of ecological welfare for food choices, food-related health consciousness, food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat-alternative rejection were used.

To assess the *importance of naturalness* in the participants' food choices, the three-item naturalness subscale from the food choice questionnaire (Steptoe et al., 1995) was used. The scale asks participants to rate, on a five-point Likert scale (from 1 = not important, to 5 = very important), how important it is to them that the food they eat in a typical day "contains no additives," "contains natural ingredients," and "contains no artificial ingredients." The scale showed good internal consistencies across the four countries, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.83 to 0.90.

To assess the *importance of ecological welfare*, the five-item ecological welfare scale, which was developed as an addition to the original food choice questionnaire (Lindeman & Väänänen, 2000) was used. The scale asks participants to rate on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 = not important, to 5 = very important) how important it is to them that the food they eat in a typical day fulfills the criteria specified in the items. Example items include "... has been produced in a way that animals have not experienced pain" and "... has been prepared in an environmentally friendly way." The scale showed good internal consistencies between $\alpha = 0.91$ and 0.94 in the four countries.

Food-related health consciousness was measured with a four-item scale partially based on the health consciousness scale (Schifferstein & Oude Ophuis, 1997), which has yielded reliable results in previous studies (Dohle et al., 2014; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019). Participants rated their agreement with the items on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree). Example items include "I think it is important to eat healthily" and "My health is dependent on how and what I eat." The scale showed internal consistencies between $\alpha = 0.79$ and 0.84 in the four countries.

Food neophobia was measured using Pliner and Hobden's (1992) 10-item food neophobia scale. Items were measured on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree). Example items include "I don't trust new foods" and "I am afraid to eat things I have never had before." The scale showed internal consistencies between $\alpha = 0.83$ and 0.90 in the four countries.

Participants' *commitment to meat* was measured with the seven-item meat commitment scale (Piazza et al., 2015). Items were measured on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree). Example items include "I can't imagine giving up meat" and "The best part of most meals is the meat portion." The scale showed internal consistencies between $\alpha = 0.93$ and 0.96 in the four countries.

To capture *negative attitudes toward meat alternatives*, the 10-item meat alternative rejection scale (Wassmann et al., 2025) was used. Items were measured on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree). Example items include "Meat substitutes will never be able to adequately replace the taste of meat" and "Meat substitutes are only a temporary trend." The scale showed internal consistencies between $\alpha = 0.92$ and 0.95 in the four countries.

2.3. Rating-based conjoint task

By varying the attributes of products according to an experimental plan, conjoint analysis allows to statistically decompose overall product ratings into the part-worth utilities of the product attributes (Orme, 2010). Rating-based conjoint analysis was most suited for answering our research questions for several reasons. First, it does not force

participants to choose between different meat analogs. Although it is possible to include a no-choice option in choice-based tasks, this would not have allowed to elicit finely graded responses and differences between the shown products. Rather than estimating how likely consumers would be to choose meat analogs over meat, our main research interest was to understand how product attributes influence consumers' preferences within the category of meat analogs. Second, it was assumed that there are different consumer segments with distinct preference structures when it comes to meat analogs. Because of its richer data and regression-based method, rating-based conjoint analysis allows for a straightforward estimation of individual-level part-worth utilities that can be used for consumer segmentation (Rao, 2014).

The two main steps in designing a conjoint study are the selection of relevant product attributes and attribute levels and the generation of an experimental design that systematically combines attribute levels into product profiles (Rao, 2014). Both steps are described in more detail below.

2.3.1. Selection of attribute levels

As explained in the introduction, the following product attributes were identified as most relevant: the type of meat product being imitated, the plant-based protein source being used as the main ingredient, the price, as well as front-of-package claims regarding nutrition and the quality of the product. An overview of the attribute levels can be found in Table 1.

For the *product type*, a plant-based burger patty and a plant-based steak were chosen as examples of products that imitate processed meat products and unprocessed whole cuts.

For the *protein source*, soy and pea were chosen, since they are both frequently used as ingredients in meat analogs (Lindberg et al., 2024) and have been shown to have different acceptance levels (Pronk et al., 2025).

To come up with realistic *price levels*, an average price for burger patties and beef steaks was established for each country by collecting prices from major supermarkets in all four countries. Prices were then scaled to portion sizes of 150 g. This led to the following prices per portion for burger patties: EUR 2.40 for Finland, EUR 2.50 for Germany, EUR 3.05 for Italy, and RSD 200 for Serbia. And to the following prices for beef steaks: EUR 5.15 for Finland, EUR 5.10 for Germany, EUR 3.80 for Italy, and RSD 330 for Serbia. Depending on the country and product type, meat analogs are currently either as expensive or more expensive than corresponding meat products (Siegrist, Green, Michel and Mathys, 2024). To cover this price range but also potentially cheaper prices for future scenarios, the price levels were defined as 115%, 100%, 85%, and 70% of the average price of a burger patty or beef steak in the corresponding countries. By using these levels as categorical attribute levels

Table 1
Attributes and attribute levels.

Product type	Protein source	Price ¹	Nutrition claim	Quality claim
Burger patty	Soy	115%	No claim	No claim
Steak	Pea	100%	High protein	Natural
		85%	Source of fiber	Country of origin ²
		70%	Source of vitamin B12	Tastes like meat

Note. ¹ Prices were calculated in relation to the average market price of burger patties and beef steaks and shown as absolute values in the local currency. Average (100%) prices for burger patties scaled to 150 g portions were EUR 2.40 for Finland, EUR 2.50 for Germany, EUR 3.05 for Italy, and RSD 200 for Serbia. Average (100%) prices for beef steaks scaled to 150 g portions were EUR 5.15 for Finland, EUR 5.10 for Germany, EUR 3.80 for Italy, and RSD 330 for Serbia. ² The national flag of each respective country was used to indicate domestic origin.

in the data analysis, it was possible to show participants different absolute prices for plant-based burger patties and steaks in the questionnaire (also known as conditional pricing, Orme, 2007).

As described in Sections 1.1.4 and 1.1.5, the present study focuses on three *nutrition claims* on meat analogs: high in protein, source of fiber, and source of vitamin B12. For the *quality claims*, the focus is on claims about the naturalness, country of origin, and meat-like taste of meat analogs. For both attributes, a fourth no-claim level was added to quantify the effectiveness of each claim against a no-claim condition.

2.3.2. Experimental design

Using an orthogonal main effects plan (generated using SPSS ORTHOPLAN), it was possible to decrease the number of product profiles to 16 while still being able to estimate unconfounded parameters for the main effect of each attribute level. In addition to these 16 profiles, two random hold-out profiles were generated for model validation. Table A1 in the Appendix shows the details of the orthogonal main effect plan. To represent the product profiles, images of plant-based burgers and steaks were designed using real photographs, which were then digitally repackaged using Adobe Illustrator. The designs of the nutrition and quality claims were inspired by designs that can be found in supermarkets. The product designs were identical across the four countries, except for the country-of-origin claim, which was accompanied by the countries' respective national flags. Fig. 1 shows an example product for each of the countries. A complete collection of images can be found in the Supplementary Materials. Participants were asked how likely they were to buy the products if they saw them in a shop and were asked to rate them on visual slider scales ranging from 0 (would never buy) to 100 (would definitely buy). The products were shown successively and in random order.

2.4. Data analysis

To simultaneously estimate sample-level and individual-level part-worth utilities and stabilize individual-level part-worth utilities (Allenby et al., 1995; Lenk et al., 1996; Rao, 2014), a hierarchical Bayesian regression was applied using the R package *brms* (Bürkner, 2017). An overall model for the complete sample was defined using product ratings as the outcome variable and product attributes as effect-coded predictors on the lower product level. The intercept and all attributes were treated as random effects so that they could vary between participants. Country membership was further included as a higher participant-level covariate to control for baseline differences in the use of the rating scales. Noninformative hyperpriors were used as a starting point to estimate the sample-level parameters, which were then used as priors to inform the posterior distributions of individual-level parameters. Posterior means of the sample-level parameters were interpreted as general part-worth utilities to discuss the overall preferences of European consumers toward the tested product attributes.

Participant-level part-worth utilities were extracted using the posterior means of the individual-level parameters. In addition, attribute importance scores were calculated for each participant by dividing the range of part-worth utilities within one attribute by the summed-up ranges of all attributes (Hair et al., 2014b). Individual-level part-worth utilities were then used to identify consumer segments with distinct preference patterns. A cluster analysis with two steps was applied (Hair et al., 2014a). First, a hierarchical cluster analysis using Euclidean distances and ward.D linkage was used to determine the number of clusters. Second, K-means clustering was used to assign participants to the determined number of clusters. The individual-level part-worth utilities were subsequently aggregated separately for each cluster to visualize the distinct preference patterns. The clusters were further characterized by comparing demographic variables and food-related psychological traits using Bonferroni-corrected ANOVAs, chi-square tests, and Bonferroni-corrected post hoc pairwise comparisons.

Finally, the influence of the four countries on the participants'

Fig. 1. Example products.

preferences was assessed by testing the distributions of the clusters across the countries using chi-square tests and Bonferroni-corrected pairwise z-tests. R (version 4.5.2) and SPSS (version 29.0.2.0) statistical software were used for the data analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Sample description

The samples in all four countries showed similar distributions of men and women and similar age distributions (see Table 2). Although women were slightly overrepresented in all four countries, the samples were, all in all, a good representation of the countries' populations. According to statistics from 2024, the proportions of women in Finland, Germany, Italy, and Serbia are 51%, 51%, 52%, 51%, respectively, and the median ages in the four countries are 43, 47, 48, and 44 years, respectively (CIA, 2025). Due to the different classification systems, it was more difficult to compare the educational attainment levels of the study samples with the countries' populations (Eurostat, 2025). In line with other statistics (Statista, 2024), a larger share of vegetarians was found in the German sample (6%) than in the samples of the other countries (<3%).

3.2. General preferences for meat analogs

To gain insights into the general impact of the product attributes on the participants' ratings, the sample-level parameters estimated by hierarchical Bayesian regression were inspected first. Fig. 2 visualizes the

part-worth utilities (posterior means) of each product attribute. Table 3 provides further information about the uncertainty around these estimates and the variability of individual-level parameters. Fig. 2 shows a clear preference for plant-based burger patties (part-worth utility of +5.15 versus -5.15 for plant-based steaks) and a gradual increase in a product's utility with a decrease in price (part-worth utility of +4.11 for the lowest price and -3.16 for the highest price). The figure also shows a slight preference for pea-based meat analogs (part-worth utility of +1.05 versus -1.05 for soy-based meat analogs). The effects of the nutrition and quality claims were negligible in comparison. These observations were mirrored in the attribute importance scores. Attribute importance was first calculated for each participant separately using individual-level parameters by dividing the range of part-worth utilities of the attribute levels within each attribute by the summed range of part-worth utilities of all attributes (Hair et al., 2014b). Therefore, the importance scores represent only the relative importance of attributes and not how strongly they affected participants' ratings on an absolute level. The mean attribute importances for the study sample were 30.9% for product type, 24.6% for protein source, 32.9% for price, 5.4% for nutrition claims, and 6.2% for quality claims.

Overall, comparable results were observed when the hierarchical Bayesian model was run separately for the four countries (see Table A2 in the Appendix). However, even stronger effects for the product type were observed in Finland and Germany than in Italy and Serbia. In addition, a slight advantage for soy-based products was found in Serbia, while pea-based products were preferred in the other three countries. The rather high importance score for the protein source in comparison to

Table 2
Sample description.

	Finland	Germany	Italy	Serbia
Data cleaning				
Number collected	1108	1103	1105	1105
Failed attention checks	183	127	307	249
Speeders	47	84	133	105
Zero variance in conjoint task	144	199	102	93
Final N ¹	793	747	677	769
Description of final samples: Mean (SD), n (%)				
Age	46 (15)	45 (15)	45 (15)	46 (14)
Gender				
Men	350 (44%)	340 (46%)	309 (46%)	346 (45%)
Women	437 (55%)	404 (54%)	365 (54%)	418 (54%)
Other or no answer	6 (<1%)	3 (<1%)	3 (<1%)	5 (<1%)
Highest degree				
No degree	15 (2%)	3 (<1%)	2 (<1%)	0 (0%)
Compulsory education	56 (7%)	33 (4%)	195 (29%)	201 (26%)
Further education	610 (77%)	562 (75%)	355 (52%)	317 (41%)
Higher education	112 (14%)	149 (20%)	125 (18%)	251 (33%)
Dietary style				
Omnivore	662 (83%)	424 (57%)	503 (74%)	524 (68%)
Flexitarian	83 (10%)	259 (35%)	144 (21%)	228 (30%)
Pescetarian	29 (4%)	11 (1%)	10 (1%)	8 (1%)
Vegetarian	15 (2%)	46 (6%)	16 (2%)	5 (<1%)
Vegan	4 (<1%)	7 (<1%)	4 (<1%)	4 (<1%)

Note. ¹Exclusion criteria overlap and therefore do not sum to final N.

Fig. 2. Sample-level part-worth utilities estimated through hierarchical Bayesian regression.

the rather low part-worth utilities for pea- and soy-based products in the overall model further indicates that different consumer clusters might have different preferences for pea and soy. Despite the high accuracy of the sample-level estimates (see credible intervals in Table 3), they might not have represented the diversity of preferences in the sample well enough. In particular, the individual-level estimates for the product types and the protein sources showed a large variability (SD = 7.98 and 8.52, respectively; see also the percentiles in Table 3). While country membership seemed to play a certain role, it was likely not the only factor that influenced the participants' preferences. To further investigate the diversity of the sample, a cluster analysis was conducted to identify and characterize consumer segments with distinct preferences.

3.3. Consumer segmentation for distinct preference patterns

To identify consumer segments with differing preference structures, a cluster analysis was conducted on the overall sample using individual-level part-worth utilities. First, a hierarchical cluster analysis with Euclidean distances and ward.D linkage was conducted. The dendrogram (see Fig. A1 in the Appendix) suggested a solution with five clusters. A solution with five clusters also resulted in the most interpretable results. In a second step, participants were therefore assigned to one of five clusters using k-means clustering. The individual-level part-worth utilities were aggregated by taking the means for each cluster to visualize the preference patterns of the clusters (see Fig. 3). The corresponding standard deviations can be found in Table A3 in the Appendix.

The first and biggest consumer cluster (54.4% of participants) was characterized by extremely low part-worth utilities for all attributes. Only the price attribute had a small effect on the ratings of these participants (part-worth utility of -3.0 for the highest price and +3.0 for the lowest price). The part-worth utilities were so close to zero that no clear preferences for the product types, protein sources, or front-of-package claims could be deduced. The product manipulations led only to slight changes in the participants' ratings in this cluster. This large cluster of consumers could therefore best be described as *indifferent* to any product manipulation.

Participants in the second biggest cluster (22.5% of participants) were also influenced by the price (part-worth utility of -3.4 for the highest price and +6.0 for the lowest price) but, even more so, by the type of meat product being imitated (part-worth utility of -9.1 for plant-based steaks and +9.1 for plant-based burger patties). Cluster 2 can therefore be described as *product type sensitive*.

Participants in the third cluster (9.5% of participants) showed a preference pattern similar to those in the product type sensitive cluster, except that the type of meat product being imitated had an even stronger effect. Products imitating steak were associated with a negative part-worth utility of -22.2, and those imitating burger patties were associated with a positive part-worth utility of +22.2. The price had a similar effect to that in the product type sensitive cluster (part-worth utility of -3.5 for the highest price and +6.8 for the lowest price). Cluster three can therefore be described as *product type focused*.

Cluster four and five (8.7% and 4.9% of participants) were both predominantly influenced by the protein sources used in meat analogs. However, while the bigger cluster four clearly preferred pea-based products (part-worth utility of +18.5) over soy-based products (part-worth utility of -18.5), the smaller cluster five showed the opposite pattern, preferring soy-based products (part-worth utility of +19.5) over pea-based products (part-worth utility of -19.5). Therefore, these two clusters can best be described as *pea preferring* and *soy preferring*.

The nutrition and quality claims had no meaningful impact on the participants' ratings in any of the identified clusters. The low standard deviations of the estimated part-worth utilities of the nutrition and quality claims (see Table 3 for the whole sample and Table A3 for the clusters) show that all participants were similarly unaffected by these claims.

The validity of the individual-level parameter estimates was tested

Table 3
Summary of the hierarchical Bayesian regression.

	Sample-level estimates			SD and percentiles of participant-level estimates				
	Posterior mean	Est. error	95% CI	SD estimate	P5	P25	P75	P95
Random effects								
Intercept	39.71	0.47	[38.75; 40.61]	25.30	1.78	18.30	58.77	82.64
Steak	-5.15	0.15	[-5.44; -4.86]	7.98	-20.78	-7.76	-0.60	2.26
Burger patty	5.15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Soy	-1.05	0.17	[-1.37; -0.72]	8.52	-14.91	-3.0	1.26	9.8
Pea	1.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Price 70%	4.11	0.11	[3.89; 4.34]	4.04	0.66	2.49	5.46	9.73
Price 85%	0.80	0.09	[0.62; 0.97]	0.15	0.79	0.79	0.80	0.81
Price 100%	-1.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Price 115%	-3.16	0.09	[-3.34; -2.98]	1.76	-4.42	-3.45	-2.83	-2.22
Vit B12 claim	-0.38	0.09	[-0.55; -0.21]	0.84	-0.72	-0.45	-0.30	-0.07
Fiber claim	-0.13	0.09	[-0.30; 0.04]	0.86	-0.47	-0.21	-0.05	0.21
Protein claim	0.67	0.09	[0.50; 0.84]	0.22	0.64	0.66	0.68	0.70
No nutrition claim	-0.16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Taste claim	-0.38	0.09	[-0.56; -0.20]	1.93	-1.70	-0.70	-0.04	0.91
Country claim	0.57	0.09	[0.41; 0.74]	0.13	0.57	0.57	0.58	0.58
Natural claim	-0.22	0.08	[-0.38; -0.05]	0.28	-0.27	-0.23	-0.21	-0.17
No quality claim	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fixed effects								
Finland	-6.99	0.80	[-8.57; -5.46]	-	-	-	-	-
Germany	-4.36	0.83	[-6.08; -2.76]	-	-	-	-	-
Italy	3.86	0.84	[2.19; 5.46]	-	-	-	-	-
Serbia	7.49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note. The hierarchical Bayesian regression was estimated using four chains, each running 4000 iterations (2000 warm-ups, and 2000 sample draws). The adapt_delta value was set to 0.95.

by analyzing the correlations between the predicted and observed product ratings as well as by the hit rate of the predictions for the two hold-out cases. Unsurprisingly, predictions were less accurate for participants in the indifferent cluster, since noise becomes more influential when participants do not show clear preferences. Predictions were, however, very accurate for participants in the other four clusters (see Appendix A4 for details).

3.4. Characterization of consumer segments

To further characterize the identified consumer segments, several food-related attitudes and motives were compared and tested using Bonferroni-corrected one-way ANOVAs and pairwise post hoc tests (see Table 4). Significant differences between the clusters were found for meat commitment, meat-alternative rejection, food neophobia, and the naturalness motive but not for the ecological welfare motive or health consciousness. The participants in the indifferent cluster had on average higher meat commitment and meat-alternative rejection values than the other clusters. Participants in the product type sensitive cluster and the product type focused cluster had on average the lowest meat-alternative rejection and food neophobia values. Participants in the pea preferring and soy preferring clusters showed on average intermediate meat-alternative rejection and food neophobia values but rather high values in the importance of naturalness.

Regarding sociodemographic variables, a chi-square test with Bonferroni-corrected pairwise z-tests found that there were relatively more men in the indifferent cluster than in the other clusters. An additional one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni-corrected post hoc pairwise comparisons found that participants in the indifferent cluster were significantly older than those in the product type sensitive and product type focused clusters.

3.5. Distribution of consumer segments in European food cultures

To obtain more detailed insights into cross-cultural differences, the distribution of the five consumer clusters was analyzed among the four countries (see Table 5). A chi-square test showed a significant association between cluster and country membership of the participants ($\chi^2(12,$

$N = 2986) = 455.93, p < .001$). The indifferent consumer cluster was by far the biggest cluster in all four countries. However, in Italy and Serbia, even more participants (67% and 60%, respectively) could be classified as indifferent compared to Finland and Germany (45% and 47%, respectively). While a good share of participants could be classified as product type focused in Finland and in Germany (13% and 20%, respectively), this consumer cluster was almost non-existent in Italy and Serbia (1% and 4%, respectively). There was a similar number of pea-preferring participants in all four countries (7%–11%), but Serbia stood out as the only country with a meaningful share of participants who preferred soy-based meat analogs (14%). Serbia also stood out as the country with the smallest proportion of participants in the product type sensitive cluster (12%).

4. Discussion

In the context of an increasing selection of plant-based meat analogs on the market (Good Food Institute, 2025) but a persisting low acceptance from consumers (Onwezen & Dagevos, 2024), the present study investigated the influence of different product attributes on consumers when they compare different meat analogs with each other. Using a rating-based conjoint analysis, it examined the effects of multiple product attributes simultaneously, which forced participants to make trade-offs. Going beyond average effects, the study further applied cluster analysis to identify consumer segments with distinct preferences and assessed how they were distributed across four European countries with different food cultures.

4.1. Preferences for plant-based meat analogs

The largest consumer cluster in all four countries responded neither to changes in the type of meat product being imitated, the main protein-rich ingredient, nor front-of-package claims, and could thus best be described as indifferent. Only price had a small effect on these consumers, with lower prices being preferred. Therefore, merely focusing on finding the best attribute configurations and emphasizing them on products packaging is unlikely to make any difference to these consumers. A large and diverse body of psychological research has shown

Mean part-worth utilities for each identified cluster

Fig. 3. Mean part-worth utilities for each identified cluster.

that strong attitudes are resistant to change (Krosnick & Petty, 1995), and research on the affect heuristic has found that people tend to ignore even relevant information when evaluating objects they already have strong affects toward (Slovic et al., 2007). However, the results of the present study only reflect consumers' perceptions of meat analogs currently on the market. If producers can improve the quality of product attributes (such as taste), and repeatedly expose consumers to such products, perceptions and preferences might change.

Besides indifferent consumers, the study also found substantial groups of consumers with clear preferences. The second- and third-largest consumer clusters both preferred low-priced meat analogs that imitate burger patties instead of steaks. Preferences for plant-based burger patties were particularly common in Finland and Germany but less so in Italy and Serbia. The higher ratings for plant-based burger patties confirm previous studies showing that consumers are more open to meat analogs that imitate processed meat products compared to whole cuts (Michel et al., 2021). The authors of the present study follow Hoek et al.'s (2011) argument that it is easier for consumers to accept a plant-based analog for a meat product that has itself been physically transformed than for a meat product in which unprocessed animal flesh is more prominent. However, familiarity with products could also play a role. Familiarity is known to increase the acceptance of food products (Tuorila & Hartmann, 2020), and consumers' familiarity with plant-based burger patties is likely to be higher because they have been on

the market for a longer time than plant-based steaks.

Previous studies have shown that the protein sources used as ingredients for meat alternatives matter to consumers (Etter et al., 2024; Onwezen et al., 2021). The present study confirms that the type of plant-based protein source matters for meat analogs, but only for a small share of consumers, characterized by rather high naturalness motives. A product's ingredients are one source of information that consumers can use to evaluate its naturalness (Román et al., 2017). Therefore, it makes sense that consumers who value the naturalness of their food focus more on the protein source used than on other product attributes. In Finland, Germany, and Italy, around 10% of consumers were influenced by the protein source used, and most preferred pea over soy as the main ingredient. This is in line with a recent multinational study showing that peas were among the most accepted and soy among the least accepted plant-based protein sources for meat alternatives in these three countries (Pronk, Etter, Michel and Siegrist, 2025). In Serbia, there are generally more people focusing on the protein source (25%), and pea- and soy-based meat analogs are preferred by an almost equal proportion of consumers. This shows that regional preferences exist and should be considered in product development. The authors of previous studies suggested that the lower acceptance of soy-based products could be explained by negative taste experiences with soy-based products such as tofu or by consumers' associations with deforestation and gene technology (Etter et al., 2024; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019). The relatively

Table 4
Comparing consumer characteristics across clusters.

	Mean [CI] / n (%) of consumer characteristics by cluster					ANOVA ¹ / Chi Square tests ²
	Indifferent (n = 1624)	Product type sensitive (n = 672)	Product type focused (n = 284)	Pea preferring (n = 261)	Soy preferring (n = 145)	
Food related characteristics						
Meat commitment	3.86 ^a [3.78; 3.95]	3.43 ^{b, c} [3.31; 3.55]	3.17 ^c [2.98; 3.36]	3.42 ^{b, c} [3.22; 3.62]	3.87 ^{a, b} [3.59; 4.15]	$F(2981,4) = 17.47, p < .001$
Meat alternative rejection	3.81 ^a [3.74; 3.88]	3.25 ^{b, c} [3.15; 3.35]	2.99 ^c [2.83; 3.14]	3.53 ^{a, b} [3.36; 3.70]	3.59 ^{a, b} [3.34; 3.84]	$F(2981,4) = 31.26, p < .001$
Food neophobia	3.45 ^a [3.40; 3.50]	3.06 ^b [2.98; 3.14]	2.92 ^b [2.79; 3.04]	3.41 ^a [3.28; 3.54]	3.44 ^a [3.27; 3.61]	$F(2981,4) = 27.15, p < .001$
Naturalness motive	4.01 ^b [3.97; 4.06]	3.76 ^c [3.68; 3.84]	3.72 ^c [3.61; 3.84]	4.24 ^a [4.13; 4.35]	4.13 ^{a, b} [3.96; 4.29]	$F(2981,4) = 18.98, p < .001$
Ecological welfare motive	3.95 ^a [3.91; 4.00]	3.96 ^a [3.89; 4.03]	3.91 ^a [3.81; 4.01]	4.09 ^a [3.99; 4.20]	3.85 ^a [3.68; 4.02]	$F(2981,4) = 2.13, p = .45$
Health consciousness	5.41 ^a [5.35; 5.47]	5.37 ^a [5.28; 5.46]	5.35 ^a [5.22; 5.49]	5.47 ^a [5.33; 5.62]	5.39 ^a [5.19; 5.60]	$F(2981,4) = 0.51, p = 1.0$
Demographics						
Age	47.0 ^a [46.3; 47.8]	43.4 ^b [42.3; 44.5]	42.2 ^b [40.6; 43.8]	46.1 ^{a, b} [44.5; 47.8]	43.2 ^{a, b} [40.7; 45.6]	$F(2981,4) = 12.63, p < .001$
Gender:	816	386	169	162	91	$\chi^2(4, N = 2969) = 28.6, p < .001$
Women ³	(50.4%) ^b	(58.0%) ^a	(59.7%) ^a	(63.0%) ^a	(62.8%) ^a	

Note. ¹ The results of the ANOVA F-tests for the food-related characteristics were Bonferroni corrected (for six tests), and each was confirmed using the more robust Welch test. Superscripts show post hoc pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction for 60 comparisons (10 pairwise comparisons for each of the six dependent variables). The results of the pairwise comparisons were further confirmed using the more robust Hochberg GT2 and the Games–Howell procedure.

² Superscripts show the results of post hoc tests comparing the proportion of women in each cluster in a pairwise manner using pairwise z-tests and Bonferroni-corrected p-values.

³ Participants who stated genders other than man or woman were ignored for testing gender distribution across the clusters due to their small sample sizes.

Table 5
Cross-tabulation of participants' country and cluster membership.

Cluster	Finland	Germany	Italy	Serbia
Indifferent	356 (45%) ^c	352 (47%) ^c	456 (67%) ^a	460 (60%) ^b
Product type sensitive	256 (32%) ^a	185 (25%) ^b	135 (20%) ^b	96 (12%) ^c
Product type focused	104 (13%) ^b	146 (20%) ^a	6 (1%) ^d	328 (4%) ^c
Pea preferring	60 (8%) ^a	53 (7%) ^a	67 (10%) ^a	81 (11%) ^a
Soy preferring	17 (2%) ^b	11 (1%) ^b	13 (2%) ^b	104 (14%) ^a
Total	793 (100%)	747 (100%)	677 (100%)	769 (100%)

Note. Significant chi-square test: $\chi^2(12, N = 2986) = 455.93, p < .001$. Superscripts show the results of post hoc tests comparing each country in a pairwise manner using pairwise z-tests and Bonferroni-corrected p-values. Within each row (cluster), countries with different letters in superscript show significantly different proportions of the respective clusters.

better standing of soy in Serbia may be explained by more positive associations with certain soy-based products or by less previous exposure to soy-based meat alternatives such as tofu. An alternative explanation could be that some Serbian consumers associate peas with certain traditional dishes, such as pea stew (*grašak sa piletinom*), and therefore perceive them as less suitable as ingredients for meat analogs.

4.2. Nutrition and quality claims

Past studies have shown that the effectiveness of nutrition and health claims depends not so much on the wording of the claims (van Trijp & van der Lans, 2007) but on the characteristics of the carrier product (Siegrist et al., 2008). Several reviews have concluded that nutrition and health claims work better on food products that already have a positive health image, that people are familiar with, and that naturally contain the nutrients they are advertising (Lähteenmäki, 2013; Steinhäuser & Hamm, 2018; Wills et al., 2012). Meat analogs do not fulfill these pre-conditions as most consumers are not yet familiar with meat analogs, and the often high degree of processing is a health concern for many (Collier et al., 2021). It is therefore likely that either consumers do not believe nutrition and health claims on meat analogs or that claims are

just not enough to override preexisting attitudes. However, it is also worth mentioning that some studies found positive effects for labels on the overall healthiness of meat analogs (Carlsson et al., 2022; Giezenaar et al., 2024). These studies compared very healthy products with very unhealthy products (e.g., health star ratings of 1.5 vs. 4.5 out of 5). Another study by Naughton et al. (2025) found positive effects for nutrition claims, especially for a high protein claim. The studies from Carlsson et al. (2022), Giezenaar et al. (2024), and Naughton et al. (2025) differ from the present study in their design as they used a choice-based conjoint design, but maybe more importantly they compared meat products with plant-based products instead of comparing products within the plant-based category.

Strong preexisting attitudes and general skepticism toward front-of-package claims are also plausible explanations for the ineffectiveness of the quality claims in the present study. Recent studies have suggested that naturalness claims have a positive effect overall (Schirmacher et al., 2023) but do not seem to work as efficiently on all kinds of products (Radaelli et al., 2025). Strong perceptions of meat analogs as highly processed (Collier et al., 2021; Varela et al., 2022) are likely to hinder the effectiveness of naturalness claims. Similarly, most consumers have negative taste expectations toward meat analogs (Giacalone et al., 2022) and are generally skeptical of taste claims (Fenko et al., 2016). With regard to country-of-origin claims, an additional factor might hinder their effectiveness. Meat analogs are not traditional food products and are not rooted in countries' cultures. This might somewhat decrease the ethnocentric motivation to choose local options for these products. Again, we observe interesting patterns when comparing our results to previous conjoint studies that contained meat and plant-based products. Origin claims so far led to mixed results with some studies showing a positive impact of origin claims (Escribano et al., 2021) and others showing a negligible impact (Giezenaar et al., 2024). Only one study tested the effect of a taste claim and found positive effects (Naughton et al., 2025). Naughton et al. (2025) used a certified taste claim which is likely to be more effective than an uncertified taste claim. Additionally, the rating-based conjoint design used in the present study allowed participants to express indifference more easily compared to the choice-based designs in the studies of Naughton et al. (2025), Escribano et al.

(2021), and Giezenaar et al. (2024), which might explain some of the different findings.

Because the studies conducted so far differ in many aspects from each other, we can only speculate how the study results would have looked like if we had focused on the comparison between plant-based products and meat. It is reasonable to assume that attributes invoke different reactions depending on which scenario is used. We believe that this is not just a methodological question but that it is also reflective of different shopping scenarios consumers can find themselves in. In most supermarkets, plant-based products are in a shelf on their own, separated from meat. If curious consumers end up having a look at these products, other attributes might be important compared to when confronted with a choice between a meat and a plant-based product.

4.3. Convincing European consumers

The results of this study offer several indications of how to best design and market meat analogs. First, price influenced consumers' preferences in all identified clusters, making it more important overall than most other attributes. If producers are able to scale their production of plant-based meat analogs up, it is likely that prices will continue to fall, which will make these products more attractive to many consumers. Additional measures to tackle the high prices of meat analogs compared to meat include cutting subsidies for meat production or introducing subsidies for the production of plant-based meat analogs (Siegrist, Michel and Hartmann, 2024).

Second, substantial groups of consumers reacted more positively toward meat analogs that imitate processed meat products (burger patties). In Germany and Finland in particular, targeting these consumer groups promises great potential, as they make up 45% of consumers, according to our samples. While it seems easier to convince consumers of plant-based burger patties and imitations of other processed meat products, one should be wary of the sustainability implications of this. If consumers replace only lower-quality processed meat products with plant-based alternatives while maintaining their consumption of high-quality cuts, the number of animals slaughtered will not change. Consequently, lower-value parts of the animal will still be produced and need to be utilized elsewhere, resulting in a less efficient overall use of the animal (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023).

In Italy and Serbia, fewer consumers showed this preference for plant-based burger patties, and more were indifferent to meat analogs. In Serbia, this could be partially explained by relatively high meat commitment and meat-alternative rejection values (Pronk et al., 2025). This fits with the description of eating cultures in the Balkans, which place a high value on meat (Krsteva-Blagoeva & Bogueva, 2021). In Italy, however, meat commitment and meat-alternative rejection are relatively low. The great importance of traditional food culture in Italy might be another explanation. Italy recently applied to UNESCO to have Italian cuisine designated as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity (Mouriquand & Barbati, 2025). Although some studies have shown signs of the Westernization of the Mediterranean diet in Italy (CIHEAM/FAO, 2015), a recent study found that protein intake is still more traditional in Italy than in other countries (Daas et al., 2025). It might therefore take more time and effort to establish meat analogs as a viable alternative in Italy, and potentially in other Mediterranean countries.

Third, showcasing soy as an ingredient in product packaging seems to be disadvantageous in most countries. It is more promising to convince consumers of pea-based meat analogs. However, some consumers in Serbia preferred soy over pea. The present study does not provide data for countries other than the researched ones; producers should therefore be aware that ingredients might be perceived differently in different countries and invest in market research to optimize their products.

Fourth, the large share of indifferent consumers showed that changes in product design alone are unlikely to change many people's attitudes toward meat analogs. Consumers with strong preexisting attitudes may

overlook meat analogs entirely. Because taste remains a crucial barrier for the consumption of meat analogs (Onwezen & Dagevos, 2024), the sensory properties of meat analogs should be further improved. Experiencing tasty products firsthand is likely to be the most powerful way to change consumers' attitudes. It is therefore also necessary to increase their exposure to such improved meat analogs, for example, through free product samples or by offering meat analogs in cafeterias.

4.4. Limitations and future research

The present study shows the extent to which product attributes increase the attractiveness of plant-based meat analogs, but it does not show how certain attribute configurations fair against meat products as they were not included in the study design. To evaluate the trade-offs between meat and plant-based products choice-based conjoint designs including plant-based and meat products would be better suited. We also encourage future studies to have a closer look at the impact of the shopping scenario (choosing among plant-based products versus choosing between meat and plant-based products) on the importance of product attributes for consumers. Studies conducted so far have too many methodological differences to answer this question, therefore experimental manipulations of the shopping scenario are needed.

The product pictures used in this study represent plant-based burger patties and steaks currently on the market. Because the industry is continuously improving its products, this study should be replicated once plant-based analogs that imitate meat more convincingly are on the market. Although this was beyond the scope of the current study, future studies could also assess whether certain product attributes interact with the type of meat product being imitated.

By investigating multiple product attributes simultaneously, the present study tried to simulate the information consumers are faced with in real shopping situations. The effects of the claims might have been suppressed by the presence of more dominant attributes such as price and product type. Furthermore, participants could have focused on these more dominant attributes to simplify the task. However, in real shopping situations even more barriers exist, such as time pressure, that can limit the effect of claims and labels (Grunert, 2011). Although the study used realistic product images as stimuli, the overall packaging had to be kept neutral so that the effects of the different attributes could be isolated. Some of the investigated claims might have been more impactful if the rest of the packaging design had been used to highlight the claimed benefits as well. Therefore, future studies should focus on only a few claims and investigate whether holistic product designs that incorporate colors, materials, shapes, and symbols to convey a claim are more effective.

It should also be noted that this study did not investigate real shopping behavior. In real life, consumers do not rate products one after the other, and they are likely to have lower attention capacities. Thus, future research should use observed instead of stated measures of consumer behavior, especially in contexts with real financial stakes.

4.5. Conclusion

Plant-based meat analogs contribute to a more sustainable food system, but consumer acceptance is currently limited. Based on the study results, industry and retail at the moment should focus on offering analogs to rather processed meat products (such as burger patties) for a low price. Promoting analogs for whole cuts (such as steaks) seems much more challenging. Research is required to investigate the reasons for this more thoroughly. Regulators and company strategists should also be aware of country differences within Europe. More efforts seem necessary to convince consumers in Italy and Serbia compared to Finland and Germany. To reach the large group of indifferent consumers they should not only rely on superficial measures such as front-of-package claims. Direct experiences with improved and satisfying products might be an option to change these consumers' attitudes. Regulators can support this

by making meat analogs more accessible in public eating settings. Additionally, measures that aim at making plant-based products more affordable compared to meat, such as removing subsidies for meat production, are likely to influence a large share of consumers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bruno Etter: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kirsten Pronk:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Fabienne Michel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michael Siegrist:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Appendix A

Table A1

Orthogonal main effect plan and holdout cases for conjoint task.

Product profile	Attributes				
	Product type	Protein source	Nutrition claim	Quality claim	Price
1	Patty	Pea	None	None	100%
2	Steak	Soy	None	Natural	115%
3	Steak	Soy	Protein	Taste	100%
4	Steak	Soy	None	Domestic	85%
5	Steak	Pea	B12	None	85%
6	Patty	Pea	Protein	Domestic	115%
7	Patty	Pea	Protein	Natural	85%
8	Patty	Pea	None	Taste	70%
9	Steak	Pea	B12	Taste	115%
10	Steak	Pea	Fiber	Natural	100%
11	Steak	Pea	Fiber	Domestic	70%
12	Patty	Soy	B12	Domestic	100%
13	Patty	Soy	Fiber	Taste	85%
14	Steak	Soy	Protein	None	70%
15	Patty	Soy	B12	Natural	70%
16	Patty	Soy	Fiber	None	115%
17 (holdout)	Patty	Pea	B12	Domestic	70%
18 (holdout)	Steak	Soy	B12	Taste	115%

Note. Product profiles were shown to the participants in randomized order.

Ethical statement

The study was approved by ETH Zurich Ethics Commission on March 4, 2025 (proposal number: 25 ETHICS-050).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. A1. Dendrogram of the cluster analysis on part-worth utilities using Euclidean distances and ward.D linkage.

Table A2

Posterior means of separate hierarchical Bayesian regressions for each country.

	Finland (n = 793)				Germany (n = 747)				Italy (n = 677)				Serbia (n = 769)			
	Post mean	SD est.	Error est.	95% CI	Post mean	SD est.	Error est.	95% CI	Post mean	SD est.	Error est.	95% CI	Post mean	SD Est.	Error Est.	95% CI
Random effects																
Intercept	32.7	22.8	0.8	[31.1; 34.3]	35.4	24.5	0.8	[33.8; 37.0]	43.7	27.1	1.0	[41.6; 45.8]	47.2	26.9	1.0	[45.3; 49.3]
Steak	-7.2	8.0	0.3	[-7.8; -6.6]	-8.1	10.7	0.4	[-8.8; -7.3]	-2.4	3.6	0.2	[-2.7; -2.1]	-2.6	5.9	0.2	[-3.1; -2.2]
Burger patty	7.2	-	-	-	8.1	-	-	-	2.4	-	-	-	2.6	-	-	-
Soy	-1.5	6.8	0.3	[-2.1; -1.0]	-1.7	6.4	0.3	[-2.1; -1.1]	-2.3	7.5	0.3	[-2.9; -1.8]	1.1	11.9	0.4	[0.2; 2.0]
Pea	1.5	-	-	-	1.7	-	-	-	2.3	-	-	-	-1.1	-	-	-
Price 70%	5.4	3.8	0.2	[5.0; 5.8]	4.5	4.0	0.2	[4.0; 4.9]	4.6	6.0	0.3	[4.0; 5.1]	2.1	2.7	0.2	[1.6; 2.5]
Price 85%	0.4	0.3	0.2	[0.0; 0.7]	0.5	0.3	0.2	[0.2; 0.9]	1.6	0.5	0.2	[1.2; 1.9]	0.9	0.4	0.2	[0.5; 1.2]
Price 100%	-2.6	-	-	-	-2	-	-	-	-1.5	-	-	-	-1.2	-	-	-
Price 115%	-3.2	0.6	0.2	[-3.5; -2.9]	-3.0	0.4	0.2	[-3.4; -2.7]	-4.7	4.2	0.2	[-5.2; -4.3]	-1.8	1.6	0.2	[-2.2; -1.5]
Vit B12 claim	-0.4	0.3	0.2	[-0.7; -0.1]	-0.4	1.4	0.2	[-0.7; -0.0]	-0.9	0.6	0.2	[-1.2; -0.6]	0.1	1.7	0.2	[-0.3; 0.5]
Fiber claim	-0.4	0.6	0.2	[-0.7; -0.1]	-0.5	1.1	0.2	[-0.8; -0.1]	0.5	1.6	0.2	[0.2; 0.8]	-0.1	0.5	0.2	[-0.5; 0.3]
Protein claim	0.5	0.3	0.2	[0.2; 0.8]	0.9	0.3	0.2	[0.5; 1.2]	1.1	1.5	0.2	[0.8; 1.5]	0.2	0.4	0.2	[-0.2; 0.6]
No nutrition claim	0.3	-	-	-	0.0	-	-	-	-0.7	-	-	-	-0.2	-	-	-
Taste claim	-0.6	2.3	0.2	[-0.9; -0.2]	-0.3	1.9	0.2	[-0.7; 0.1]	-0.7	2.5	0.2	[-1.0; -0.3]	-0.0	0.8	0.2	[-0.4; 0.3]
Country claim	0.9	0.5	0.2	[0.5; 1.2]	0.8	0.2	0.2	[0.5; 1.1]	0.6	0.3	0.2	[0.3; 0.9]	0.1	0.3	0.2	[-0.3; 0.4]
Natural claim	-0.2	0.4	0.2	[-0.6; 0.1]	-0.6	1.0	0.2	[-0.9; -0.2]	-0.1	0.4	0.2	[-0.4; 0.3]	0.0	0.6	0.2	[-0.4; 0.4]
No quality claim	-0.1	-	-	-	0.1	-	-	-	0.2	-	-	-	-0.1	-	-	-

Note. Each model treated the intercept and the slopes of the product attributes as random effects that could vary between participants (higher-level grouping variable). The model was estimated using the *brms* R package. Four chains, each with 4000 iterations (of which 2000 were warm-up draws and 2000 were sampling draws), were used for estimating the posteriors. The noninformative default priors for a Gaussian model were used as hyperpriors, and an adapt_delta value of 0.95 was used.

Table A3
Mean and standard deviation of part-worth utilities by consumer cluster.

Attribute levels	Indifferent (n = 1624)		Product type sensitive (n = 672)		Product type focused (n = 284)		Pea preferring (n = 261)		Soy preferring (n = 145)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Intercept	35.1	28.9	46.3	20.7	47.0	13.3	41.8	16.0	42.3	16.6
Product type										
Steak	-0.8	3.0	-9.1	3.1	-22.7	6.0	-3.5	4.5	-3.3	4.9
Burger patty	0.8	3.0	9.1	3.1	22.7	6.0	3.5	4.5	3.3	4.9
Protein source										
Soy	-0.3	3.2	-0.6	3.8	-0.9	4.1	-18.5	7.7	19.5	7.5
Pea	0.3	3.2	0.6	3.8	0.9	4.1	18.5	7.7	-19.5	7.5
Price										
70%	3.0	1.8	6.0	3.0	6.8	3.8	3.6	2.5	3.8	2.9
85%	0.8	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.8	0.0
100%	-0.8	1.8	-3.4	2.9	-4.1	3.7	-1.2	2.6	-1.6	3.2
115%	-3.0	0.5	-3.4	0.8	-3.5	0.8	-3.2	0.8	-3.0	0.9
Nutrition claim										
Vit B12	-0.4	0.1	-0.4	0.2	-0.4	0.2	-0.5	0.3	-0.3	0.3
Fiber	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.2	-0.2	0.3	-0.2	0.3	-0.1	0.3
Protein	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0
No claim	-0.2	0.3	-0.2	0.4	-0.1	0.4	0.0	0.5	-0.3	0.5
Quality claim										
Taste	-0.4	0.6	-0.4	1.0	-0.4	1.1	-0.4	1.1	-0.2	1.1
Country	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.0
Natural	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0
No claim	0.0	0.7	0.1	1.0	0.0	1.1	0.1	1.1	-0.1	1.1

A4: Model validation.

The fit of the individual-level parameter estimates was tested by calculating an expected rating score for each of the 16 product profiles for each participant. The Pearson correlations between the expected and observed ratings of the 16 products were then calculated separately for each participant. Because the estimates were likely to be less informative for participants in the indifferent cluster, the correlations were then aggregated by cluster. The following average correlations were found: $r = 0.50$ for the indifferent cluster, $r = 0.80$ for the product type sensitive cluster, $r = 0.91$ for the product type focused cluster, $r = 0.89$ for the pea preferring cluster, and $r = 0.88$ for the soy preferring cluster. To validate the models further, the hit rates for the two holdout cases were calculated. The individual-level models were able to predict the rank order of the two hold-out cases 62% of the time in the indifferent cluster, 92% of the time in the product type sensitive cluster, 97% of the time in the product type focused cluster, 97% of the time in the pea preferring cluster, and 87% of the time in the soy preferring cluster. Together, this shows that individual-level parameter estimates can reproduce participants' preference ratings and predict new ratings in four out of five clusters. In the indifferent cluster, however, the estimates are much less informative, and noise is more likely to have an impact on the rating scores.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2026.105944>.

Data availability

All data is made available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19661808>

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